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Perception Of Fuel Subsidy Removal Among Farming Households In Imo State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined how farming households in Imo State perceive the removal of fuel subsidy. Specifically, it explored their level of awareness, their general perception of fuel subsidy, the reasons they believe led to its removal, and the perceived effects on their livelihoods. A total of 120 farming households were selected through a multistage sampling technique. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics. Findings revealed that the majority of respondents (90%) were aware of the fuel subsidy removal. They perceived the subsidy as a government-provided benefit ($\bar{x} = 3.0$), either as a direct or indirect payment or privilege granted to individuals, private firms, households, or government entities to support public objectives ($\bar{x} = 3.0$). Respondents largely believed that the removal of the subsidy was intended by the government to increase fuel prices and, consequently, generate more revenue. The perceived effects of the subsidy removal included a rise in fuel pump prices ($\bar{x} = 3.5$), higher transportation costs for farm produce ($\bar{x} = 3.5$), increased food prices ($\bar{x} = 3.5$), and reduced access to agricultural machinery and equipment ($\bar{x} = 2.9$), among others. The study concluded that farming households viewed the removal of fuel subsidy as significantly impacting their economic well-being. It recommended that the government promote investment in alternative renewable energy sources and the power sector to reduce dependence on fuel. Additionally, efforts should be made to lower fuel prices to make them more affordable for farming communities.

Keywords: farming households, fuel subsidy removal, fuel prices

INTRODUCTION

The Nigerian government initially introduced fuel subsidies as a strategy to stabilize fuel prices and make petroleum products affordable for the general population. Since the 1970s, fuel subsidies have been used to cushion citizens from the effects of volatile global oil prices, allowing Nigerians to purchase fuel at prices below the international market rate. The primary goal of this policy was to reduce the economic burden of high fuel prices on households and businesses. However, despite its benefits, the fuel subsidy regime has placed a considerable strain on public finances. Between 2011 and 2015 alone, the government reportedly spent over \$35 billion on fuel subsidies (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2015), diverting funds that could have been invested in infrastructure and social welfare programs. Subsidies, generally defined as financial support extended by the government to sectors, institutions, businesses, or individuals, are intended to promote specific economic and social goals (Academia, 2023). According to Alozie (2009), subsidies function to keep the prices of goods and services below market levels for consumers or producers. In Nigeria, the government has periodically attempted to remove fuel subsidies due to their unsustainable fiscal burden. Efforts to eliminate the subsidies began during President

Olusegun Obasanjo's administration in 1999, but public resistance halted the reform. A more decisive step came in May 2016, when President Muhammadu Buhari announced the full removal of fuel subsidies, which sparked widespread protests due to the sharp rise in fuel prices (Adamu, 2023). Over the past three decades, subsidy removal has remained a contentious issue due to its significant socioeconomic implications, particularly for low-income households (Adenikinju, 2009).

From a political economy perspective, the removal of fuel subsidies is challenging because it affects a wide range of Nigerian households. In states like Imo, the withdrawal of fuel subsidies has had a notable impact on farming communities. Higher fuel prices have increased the costs of operating agricultural machinery and transporting produce to markets. This has translated into higher production costs and reduced profit margins for farmers, which may lead to a decline in agricultural productivity and household incomes. Furthermore, rising fuel prices can exacerbate transportation expenses, making it more difficult for farmers to access markets and earn sustainable incomes. The removal of subsidies also risks deepening income inequality, as wealthier households are better positioned to absorb the rising costs, while low-income farming families face heightened economic hardship. This situation could further increase poverty levels among farming households struggling to meet their basic needs. Understanding how farming households perceive the removal of fuel subsidies is essential for policymakers and stakeholders in the agricultural sector. Such insight can help anticipate the challenges and identify support mechanisms to cushion the adverse effects of the policy shift. This study, therefore, aims to fill existing gaps in knowledge by investigating the implications of fuel subsidy removal on farming households in Imo State.

In light of the above, the study was guided by the following research questions:

- i. Are farming households aware of the removal of fuel subsidies?
- ii. What are the perceptions of farming households regarding fuel subsidies?
- iii. What do farming households perceive as the reasons behind the removal of fuel subsidies?
- iv. How has the removal of fuel subsidies affected farming households in Imo State?

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted in Imo State, Nigeria, which is located in the southeastern part of the country and is known for its significant farming population. Farming serves as the primary occupation for many households in the state. A multistage sampling procedure was used for this study. Purposive sampling was initially employed to select regions with a high concentration of farming households. Four local government areas (LGAs) were selected from each of Imo state's three agricultural zones Owerri, Okigwe, and Orlu making a total of 12 LGAs. From these 12 LGAs, one community was randomly chosen from each, resulting in a total of 12 communities. Ten farming households were then selected from each community, yielding a sample size of 120 households. A list of farming households was obtained from each of the selected villages. Data were collected using questionnaires. To address Objective I, descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentage were used. For Objectives II, III, and IV, mean scores were analyzed. A 4-point Likert-type scale was applied, with the following ratings: SA (Strongly Agree) = 4, A (Agree) = 3, D (Disagree) = 2, and SD (Strongly Disagree) = 1. The scores were summed and divided by the number of scale points to calculate a discriminating index of 2.50, derived from $(4+3+2+1)/4 = 2.50$. This index was used to assess the causes and effects of fuel subsidy removal, as perceived by the farming households. According to the perceptions of the farming households, the decision rule indicated that any variable with a mean score equal to or greater than 2.50 was considered a cause of fuel subsidy removal, while variables below this threshold were not accepted. A similar rule was applied for the perceived effects: any statement with a mean score of 2.50 or higher was recognized as a perceived effect of the fuel subsidy removal on farming households.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results presented in Figure 1 indicate that the majority (90%) of farming households were aware of the removal of the fuel subsidy. This awareness is important as it allows farming households to understand the potential impacts of the subsidy removal on their agricultural activities, which is essential for promoting sustainable and inclusive agricultural development. This finding contrasts with the study by Raji *et al.* (2018), which suggested that a lack of awareness and understanding among farming households regarding fuel subsidy removal could impede farmers' ability to adapt and make informed decisions.

Figure1: Awareness of fuel subsidy removal among farming households

The findings presented in Table 1 indicate that farming households viewed the fuel subsidy in various ways: as a benefit provided by the government to individuals ($\bar{x} = 3.0$), as financial aid or grants given to specific individuals to stimulate economic activities or achieve certain objectives ($\bar{x} = 3.1$), as direct or indirect payments or privileges granted by the government to private firms, households, or other government units to promote public goals ($\bar{x} = 3.0$), as a transfer of funds from the government to an entity ($\bar{x} = 2.8$), and as a form of government expenditure aimed at stabilizing the economy for individuals, households, and businesses ($\bar{x} = 3.0$). The high level of perception and acceptance of the subsidy could be linked to factors such as the relatively high formal education of farming households, their extension contact, and cooperative membership. This finding aligns with the Institute for Sustainable Development (IISD, 2018), which studied public perceptions of subsidies and found that subsidies are often viewed as a means to keep prices low and support economic growth.

Table 1: Fuel Subsidy Perception among farming households

	Fuel subsidy perception	SA	A	DA	SA	MS	remark
a)	Subsidy is a benefit given to an individual business or institution usually by the government.	48	44	16	12	3.0	Accepted
b)	Subsidy is a financial aid or grant given by the governments to certain individuals, organization or industries to promote economic activities or achieve specific objectives.	52	40	20	8	3.1	Accepted
c)	Subsidy is a direct or indirect payment, or privilege granted by a government to private firms, households or other governmental units in order to promote a public objective.	52	32	28	8	3.0	Accepted
d)	Subsidy is a transfer of money from the government to an entity.	44	28	32	16	2.8	Accepted
e)	Subsidy is a type of government expenditure for individuals and households as well as businesses with the aim of stabilizing the economy.	60	28	12	20	3.0	Accepted

Source: field survey data, Discriminating index $2.5, \geq 2.5 = \text{Acceptance}, > = \text{Rejection}$

Causes of Fuel subsidy Removal as perceived by Farming Households

The findings in Table 2 revealed that farming households identified the following as causes of fuel subsidy removal: revenue generation ($\bar{x} = 3.0$), reduction of corruption in the oil sector ($\bar{x} = 2.6$), and an increase in fuel prices ($\bar{x} = 3.0$). Farming households perceived the removal of the fuel subsidy as a strategy by the government to raise fuel prices and generate more revenue. This perspective contrasts with the findings of Fischer (2019), who argued that the government views the removal of fuel subsidies as a means to promote market efficiency and enhance competitiveness.

Table 2: Causes of fuel subsidy removal as perceived by farming households

Perceived causes	strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	strongly disagree	mean score	Remark
a) Governments need to generate revenue	56	32	16	16	3.0	Accepted
b) Reduce corruption in the oil sector	32	40	24	24	2.6	Accepted
c) Encourage local refining and production	1	1	18	100	1.15	Rejected
d) Reduce dependency on imported fuel	0	0	19	101	1.2	Rejected
e) Encourage competition and market efficiency	2	7	21	90	1.5	Rejected
f) Increase in fuel prices	48	40	24	8	3.0	Accepted

Source: field survey data, Discriminating index $2.5, \geq 2.5 = \text{Acceptance}, > = \text{Rejection}$

Perceived effects of fuel subsidy removal among farming households in Imo State

The results in Table 3 showed that farming households perceived the following as effects of the fuel subsidy removal: an increase in fuel pump prices ($\bar{x} = 3.5$), higher transportation costs for farm produce ($\bar{x} = 3.5$), rising food prices ($\bar{x} = 3.5$), increased prices of farm produce ($\bar{x} = 3.2$), reduced farming profitability ($\bar{x} = 2.9$), limited access to agricultural machinery and equipment ($\bar{x} = 2.9$), higher unemployment in the agricultural sector ($\bar{x} = 3.3$), increased transportation costs for getting produce to the market ($\bar{x} = 3.4$), and higher costs of production and farming activities like ploughing and clearing ($\bar{x} = 2.8$). The increase in fuel pump prices for domestic petroleum products in Nigeria has affected economic activities reliant on petroleum as an energy source. Consequently, farmers now spend more on transporting their produce to markets. The rise in fuel costs has led transport operators across Nigeria to raise transportation fares to cover their operational and maintenance costs (Kyarem, 2023). This aligns with the findings of Akinyemi et al. (2017), who reported that the removal of fuel subsidies resulted in higher production costs for farmers, which negatively impacted their overall welfare and income, ultimately leading to a decrease in agricultural productivity and profitability for farming households.

Table 3: perceived effects of fuel subsidy removal

Perceived effects	Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	MS	SD	Remark
a) Increased cost of transportation for farm inputs.	84	28	-	8	3.5	0.80	Accepted
b) Increased price of farm produce.	48	56	12	4	3.2	0.76	Accepted
c) Reduced profitability of farming.	44	36	32	8	2.9	0.95	Accepted
d) Limited access to agricultural machinery and equipment.	32	56	28	4	2.9	0.79	Accepted
e) Increased fuel pump price.	68	36	16	-	3.5	0.92	Accepted
f) Increased food prices.	76	32	12	-	3.5	0.67	Accepted
g) Decreased income for farmers.	52	32	24	12	3.0	1.02	Accepted
h) Increased unemployment in the agricultural sector.	64	32	20	4	3.3	0.86	Accepted
i) Increased cost of transportation of produce to the market	64	44	8	4	3.4	0.76	Accepted
j) Increased cost of production/farming activities like ploughing, clearing etc.	32	48	28	12	2.8	0.93	Accepted

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, farming households were aware of the fuel subsidy removal and identified the need to generate revenue, reduce corruption in the oil sector, and the increase in fuel prices as the primary causes of the subsidy removal. They perceived the following as the effects of the fuel subsidy removal: increased fuel pump prices, higher transportation costs for farm produce, rising food prices, increased prices of farm produce, limited access to agricultural machinery and equipment, reduced agricultural productivity, decreased income for farmers, higher unemployment in the agricultural sector, increased transportation costs for getting produce to the market, and increased costs of production and farming activities such as ploughing and clearing.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the key findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. The government should implement targeted support programs and policies to help farming households adjust to higher fuel prices, ensuring they continue to have access to affordable inputs and transportation services.
- ii. Extension agents should be encouraged to promote the adoption of sustainable and energy-efficient agricultural practices to reduce reliance on fossil fuels. This could involve promoting organic farming methods, the use of renewable energy sources, and the adoption of precision agriculture techniques.
- iii. The government and NGOs should provide financial support and incentives to farming households for investing in energy-efficient technologies and equipment, such as solar-powered irrigation systems, energy-efficient machinery, and vehicles.

- iv. Extension agents should strengthen agricultural cooperatives and farmer organizations to facilitate collective purchasing of fuel and equipment, enabling farming households to achieve cost savings and enhance their negotiating power.
- v. Extension experts should employ subject matter specialists to provide training and capacity-building programs aimed at educating farming households about alternative energy sources, energy-saving practices, and financial management strategies to cope with higher fuel costs.

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